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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF STABILITY-INDICATING REVERSED-PHASE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHIC METHOD FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF METFORMIN AND CANAGLIFLOZIN IN PRESENCE OF THEIR DEGRADATION PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

A reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatographic method was developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin in the presence of their degradation products. Analytes were separated on Hypersil C18, 250x4.6 mm, 5 μ m column using an isocratic elution mode having a mobile phase composition of 50 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): methanol (50:50 v/v). Analytes were detected at a wavelength of 225 nm. A 20 μ L fixed-loop injector was used for the injection of samples at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. The optimized method was validated as per ICH Q2 guidelines. The retention times of Metformin and Canagliflozin were 3.47 min and 5.28 min respectively. The linearity was assessed by analysis of a combined standard solution in the range of 5-20 μ g/ml for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. The correlation coefficient for calibration curves of Metformin and Canagliflozin were 0.999 and 0.999 respectively. Accuracy was calculated in terms of percentage recovery and was within the limits of 98-102%. Inter and Intra-day precisions were calculated as percentage relative standard deviation and were less than two percent. Limit of detection and limit of quantitation were within the limits of ICH-Q2 guidelines. Method was robust with % RSD values <2% with the deliberate changes in the composition of mobile phase, changes in the pH or change in the flow rate. Significant degradation was observed in the presence of acidic, basic, neutral, oxidative and photolytic stress conditions. The proposed RP-HPLC method is simple, precise, accurate, robust and reproducible and was successfully able to separate, identify and quantify the Metformin and Canagliflozin in the presence of their degradation products implies the stability indicating nature and specificity of the method.

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INTRODUCTION

Type 2 Diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is the most prevalent metabolic disease worldwide. Inadequate management and control of hyperglycemia in patients with T2DM lead to long-term complications due to the chronic and progressive nature of the disease arising from pathophysiology of beta-cell dysfunction, insulin resistance and increased hepatic glucose output. Patients with T2DM often require a combination of therapeutic agents to achieve glycemic control over the long term [1-6]. The American Diabetes Association and the European Association for the Study of Diabetes have recently recommended that patients who are inadequately controlled on metformin use additional anti-hyperglycemic agents that have complimentary mechanisms of action [3].

Metformin is the most commonly prescribed oral antidiabetic agent. It is recommended as a first-line therapy in the management of T2DM when hyperglycemia is not satisfactorily managed by diet alone. Metformin decreases hepatic glucose production and intestinal absorption of glucose, and improves insulin sensitivity by increasing peripheral glucose uptake and utilization [7,8]. Metformin is chemically 1- carbamiimidamido-N, N-dimethylmethaniimidamide (Figure-1a). Metformin immediate release (IR) tablets are available at 500, 850, and 1,000 mg strengths of metformin hydrochloride (HCl) and are administered 2 or 3 times daily up to a maximum recommended a daily dose of 2,550 mg in adults [9,10].

Canagliflozin (Invokana®; Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Inc.) belongs to a novel class of orally active inhibitors of renal sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2). It decreases the extent of glucose reabsorption from the proximal tubules of the kidney, thereby increasing urinary glucose excretion (UGE) and decreasing plasma glucose levels in patients with hyperglycemia [11-21]. Canagliflozin is chemically (2S, 3R, 4R, 5S, 6R)-2-(3-([5-(4-fluorophenyl) thiophene-2-yl] methyl)-4-methyl phenyl)-6-(hydroxyl methyl) oxane-3, 4, 5-triol (Figure-1b). It is used as an adjunct to diet and exercise to improve glycemic control in adults with T2DM in numerous countries worldwide. The recommended dose of Canagliflozin is 100 or 300 mg once daily (QD) [22-25].

Canagliflozin's mechanism of action differs from other classes of oral antidiabetic agents such as dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors (DPP-4), sulfonylureas, and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor agonists (PPAR), which makes it an ideal candidate for combination therapies with metformin and other antidiabetic agents. In Phase 3 studies of Canagliflozin (100 and 300 mg QD) on participants with T2DM who were inadequately controlled on metformin monotherapy, dual therapy with metformin plus sulphonylurea or metformin plus pioglitazone, the addition of Canagliflozin significantly improved glycemic control and was associated with a low incidence of hypoglycaemia and clinically meaningful weight loss at all doses [25-27].

Figure 1. Chemical structures of Metformin and Canagliflozin

A combined formulation consisting of both metformin and Canagliflozin in a single tablet would potentially offer an increased convenience and a subsequent potential for increased therapy compliance [28,29]. Invokamet TM (Janssen Pharmaceuticals, Inc.) is an immediate release (IR) fixed-dose combination (FDC) tablet of Canagliflozin (50 or 150 mg) and metformin (500, 850, or 1,000 mg) that has received regulatory approval in the European Union for the treatment of T2DM in adults to improve glycemic control in patients not adequately controlled on their maximally tolerated doses of metformin alone or combined with other glucose-lowering medicinal products including insulin, and patients already treated with combination of Canagliflozin and metformin as separate IR tablets [30].

Various ultraviolet spectroscopic and high performance liquid chromatographic assay methods were reported for the estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin individually and in combination with other drugs [31-59]. According to a literature survey, not a single method was reported for the validated stability indicating method development for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin by reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography in combined tablet dosage forms. Hence, an attempt has been made to develop and validate stability indicating reversed-phase liquid chromatographic method for simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin and all possible impurities in combined dosage forms in accordance with the ICH guidelines.

Advantages of simultaneous stability studies are the identification of new impurities in addition to those studied for stability assays of Metformin and Canagliflozin alone, to understand mutual induction and/or inhibition of rates of degradation and to identify common impurities of both drugs in combined dosage forms [59].

This communication represents the report for a simple, precise, accurate, sensitive and reproducible stability indicating method for the simultaneous estimation of Metformin and Canagliflozin.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation

Analytes were scanned between 200–400 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, model UV-1700). Experiments were carried out using Shimadzu prominence Modular HPLC system with LC 20AT solvent delivery unit, CBM 20A system controller, SIL 20A auto-sampler, CTO 20A column oven and SPD 20 A UV Detector. Data was recorded and evaluated using Spinchrom software as the data integrator. 20 μ L fixed-loop injector was used for the injection of the samples with the flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. The pH of the solutions was measured with the pH meter (Mettler Toledo, S20K). Refluxing of the drugs in specific degradation conditions were carried out using a rotavapor (R-300, Buchi). Shimadzu ATX-124 analytical balance was used for weighing.

Reagents and Chemicals

The reference materials of Metformin and Canagliflozin were purchased from Mesochem Technology, Inc., Beijing, China. Methanol and Water were used of HPLC grade and purchased from Fisher Scientific. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Company. Commercial tablets (INVOKAMET: dosage Metformin 500 mg and Canagliflozin 150 mg) were purchased from a local pharmacy.

Selection of wavelength

Standard solution of Metformin (10 μ g/mL) and Canagliflozin (10 μ g/mL) were scanned between 200–400 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer. Wavelength was selected from the overlay spectra of above solutions.

Chromatographic separation

Analytes were separated on Hypersil C18, 250x4.6 mm, 5 μ m column using an isocratic elution mode having mobile phase composition of 50 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): methanol (50:50 v/v). The detection was carried out at the wavelength of 225 nm. Peak area, peak height, retention time and resolution were recorded using Spinchrom software. 20 μ L fixed-loop injector was used for the injection of the samples with the flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹.

Preparation of standard solutions

10 mg of Metformin and 10 mg of Canagliflozin were separately weighed and transferred to previously labeled 100 mL volumetric flasks and volume was made up to the mark with methanol to obtain 100 μ g/mL of Metformin standard stock solution and 100 μ g/mL of Canagliflozin standard stock solution respectively. 1 mL from the Metformin stock solution and 1 mL from Canagliflozin stock solution were transferred into respectively labeled 10 mL volumetric flasks and volume was made up to the mark by mobile phase to obtain a standard solution of mixtures of Metformin (10 μ g/mL) and Canagliflozin (10 μ g/mL).

Method Validation

System suitability test

System suitability test is an integral part of the chromatographic method. These tests are used to verify that the resolution and reproducibility of the system are adequate for the analysis to be performed. System suitability tests are based on the concept that the equipment, electronics, analytical operations and samples constitute an integral system that can be evaluated as a whole. System suitability testing provides assurance that the method will provide accurate and precise data for its intended use [40].

Linearity

The linearity was assessed by analysis of combined standard solution in a range of 5–20 μ g/mL for each of the Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Precision

Results were expressed as percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) or coefficient of variance.

Repeatability

A standard solution containing 10 μ g/mL of each of the Metformin and Canagliflozin was injected six times, areas of peaks were measured and % RSD was calculated to determine the repeatability of the method.

Intra- day and inter-day precision

A standard solution containing 5, 10 and 15 μ g/mL of each of the Metformin and Canagliflozin were analyzed three times on the same day for the determination of intra-day precision and on three different days for the determination of inter-day precision and % R.S.D was calculated.

Accuracy

Accuracy was calculated at three different levels in terms of % recovery by spiking known amount of standard solution (80%, 100% and 120%) to the solution of a synthetic mixture of marketed formulations.

Specificity and selectivity

The specificity of the method was established through the study of resolution factors of the drug peak from the nearest resolving peak and also among all other peaks.

Limit of detection and Limit of quantitation (LOD and LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ were estimated at signal-to-noise ratios of 3:1 and 10:1, respectively, by injecting a series of dilute solutions with known concentrations.

Robustness

Robustness of the method was investigated by varying the chromatographic conditions, such as, changing the flow rate by $\pm 10\%$ i.e. 0.8 ml/min and 1.2 ml/min; changing the ratio of mobile phase was with ± 2 i.e. buffer: methanol (48:52) and buffer: methanol (52:48); and changing the pH of the buffer in the mobile phase with $\pm 0.2\%$ i.e. 2.8 and 3.2. Robustness of the developed method was indicated by the overall % RSD between the data, at each variable condition.

Analysis of marketed formulation

Twenty tablets of marketed formulation Invokamet with the label claim of 500 mg of metformin and 150 mg of Canagliflozin were weighed individually and finely powdered. Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg of Metformin and 15 mg Canagliflozin was weighed accurately and transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask. The analytes were extracted with 5 ml methanol by sonication in the ultra-sonicator bath and then the volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase. The solution was filtered through Whatman filter paper no. 42. One mL from this solution was transferred to 25 ml volumetric flask and volume was made up to the mark with mobile phase to obtain the concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Metformin and 6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Canagliflozin. Samples were analyzed using the developed assay. The areas of resulting peak were measured at 225 nm.

Stress degradation studies**Acid hydrolysis**

Forced degradation in acidic condition was performed by adding 1 ml of standard solution of mixtures of Metformin (1 mg/mL) and Canagliflozin (1 mg/mL) to 10 ml each of methanol and 0.1 M hydrochloric acid and refluxing the mixture at 70°C for 2 hours (n=3). The solution was then allowed to reach at room temperature, neutralized to pH 7 by the addition of 0.1 M sodium hydroxide, and diluted to 100 ml with the mobile phase so as to get a final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg of Metformin and 15 mg Canagliflozin was also treated with described acidic conditions.

Alkaline hydrolysis

Alkali-induced, forced degradation was performed by adding 1 ml of a standard solution of a mixture of Metformin (1 mg/mL) and Canagliflozin (1 mg/mL) to 10 ml each of methanol and 0.1 M sodium hydroxide and refluxing the mixture at 70°C for 2 hours. The solution was then allowed to reach at room temperature, neutralized to pH 7 by the addition of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid, and diluted to 100 ml with the mobile phase to get a final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg of Metformin and 15 mg Canagliflozin was also treated with described alkaline conditions.

Oxidative degradation

To evaluate the effect of oxidizing conditions, 1 ml of the standard solution of a mixture of Metformin (1 mg/mL) and Canagliflozin (1 mg/mL) was added to 2 ml of 3% hydrogen peroxide solution and the mixture was refluxed at 70°C for 2 hours. The solution was then allowed to reach room temperature and diluted to 100 ml with the mobile phase to get a final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg of Metformin and 15 mg Canagliflozin was also treated with described oxidative degradation conditions.

Thermal degradation

To evaluate the effect of temperature, 1 ml of a standard solution of a mixture of Metformin (1 mg/mL) and Canagliflozin (1 mg/mL) was stored at 105°C in a hot air oven for 1.5 hours. The solution was then allowed to reach room temperature and diluted to 100 ml with the mobile phase to get a final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg of Metformin and 15 mg Canagliflozin was also treated with described thermal degradation condition.

Photolytic degradation

To study the effect of UV light, a mixture of Metformin and Canagliflozin, 25 mg each, was exposed to short and long wavelength UV light (254 nm and 366 nm, respectively) for 24 hours, and then dissolved in 10 ml of methanol. The volume was made up by the mobile phase in a 50 ml volumetric flask and then 1 ml of stock solution was further diluted with the mobile phase to give a solution of final concentration equivalent to 10 µg/ml for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin. Tablet powder equivalent to 50 mg of Metformin and 15 mg Canagliflozin was also treated with described photolytic degradation conditions.

Twenty microliters of the resulting solutions were injected into the HPLC system and the chromatograms were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method development

As Metformin and Canagliflozin both showed absorbance response at a wavelength of 225 nm, it was selected as a wavelength of detection. Figure 2 represents the overlying UV spectra of Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Figure 2: Overlay UV Spectrum of Metformin and Canagliflozin showing selection of wavelength detection.

For method development, reverse phase liquid chromatography was chosen because of its simple and convenient use in terms of efficiency, stability and reproducibility. Analytes were separated on Hypersil C18, 250 x 4.6 mm, 5µm column using an isocratic elution mode having mobile phase composition of 50 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): methanol (50:50 v/v). Analytes were detected at 225 nm. 20µL fixed-loop injector was used for the injection of the samples with the flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹. Retention time was 3.47 min and 5.283 min for Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Chromatogram of Metformin and Canagliflozin in 50 mM potassium di-hydrogen phosphate buffer (pH 3.0): methanol (50:50 v/v) with flow rate-1.0 ml/min.

Method validation

The method was validated as per ICH guidelines with respect to parameters like linearity, precision, accuracy, specificity, and robustness.

The number of theoretical plates, peak tailing and resolution factor were determined to define system suitability parameters for Metformin and Canagliflozin. The results for system suitability data are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: System suitability parameters for Metformin and Canagliflozin.

System Suitability Parameters	Metformin	Canagliflozin
Theoretical plates per column (N)	9605	6300
Symmetry factor/Tailing factor	1.286	1.417
Resolution	8.892	

Linearity and range were assessed by analysis of combined standard solution in the range of 5-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for Metformin and Canagliflozin, each respectively. Standard calibration curve for Metformin and Canagliflozin are represented as Figure 4 and 5, respectively.

Figure 4: Standard Calibration curve of Metformin (5-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).

Figure 5: Standard Calibration curve of Canagliflozin (5-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$).

The data for regression analysis is listed in Table 2. A standard solution containing 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for each of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively was injected six times and areas of peaks were measured to determine the repeatability of the method. % R.S.D. value for the determination of repeatability is represented in Table 3.

Table 2: Results from regression analysis for Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Description	Values Metformin	Canagliflozin
Linearity and range	5-20 µg/ml	5-20 µg/ml
Regression co-efficient	0.999	0.999
Slope (m)	72.75	126.4
Intercept (c)	5.684	9.215

Table 3: Repeatability data for Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Metformin				Canagliflozin			
Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak Area	Mean ± S.D (n=6)	% R.S.D	Conc. (µg/ml)	Peak Area	Mean ± S.D (n=6)	% R.S.D
10	722.142	724.045±3.522	0.486	10	1258.405	1253.955 ±6.251	0.499
	719.964						
	723.561						
	722.103						
	727.161						
	729.340						
					1248.954		
					1253.564		
					1245.595		
					1254.289		
					1262.922		

A standard solution containing (5,10,15 µg/ml) Metformin and (5,10,15 µg/ml) Canagliflozin were analyzed three times on the same day for the determination of intra-day precision and on three different days for the determination of inter-day precision. % R.S.D values for intra-day and inter-day precision are represented in Table 4. The accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from the synthetic mixture of marketed formulation at three levels of standard addition. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 4: Intra-day and Inter-day precision for Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Metformin			Canagliflozin		
Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean ± S.D (n=6)	% R.S.D	Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean ± S.D (n=6)	% R.S.D
Intra-day precision					
5	359.241 ± 0.367	0.102	5	625.084 ± 3.405	0.545
10	729.132 ± 2.773	0.380	10	1261.812 ± 2.860	0.226
15	1087.211 ± 2.433	0.224	15	1885.129 ± 9.016	0.478
Inter-day precision					
5	359.046 ± 0.667	0.186	5	621.383 ± 4.539	0.730
10	724.270 ± 6.917	0.955	10	1244.327 ± 15.397	1.237
15	1073.888 ± 10.787	1.004	15	1856.234 ± 28.808	1.552

Table 5: Accuracy in terms of % recovery for Metformin and Canagliflozin.

Conc. Level (%)	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Amount of Standard Added (µg/ml)	Metformin			Canagliflozin		
			Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	% Mean Recovery ± S.D	Amount Recovered (µg/ml)	% Recovery	% Mean Recovery ± S.D
80 %	5	4	4.038	100.949	100.994 ± 0.296	3.978	99.443	99.961 ± 1.187
	5	4	4.029	100.722		3.965	99.122	
	5	4	4.052	101.310		4.053	101.319	
100 %	5	5	5.025	100.498	100.304 ± 0.332	5.004	100.074	98.988 ± 0.942
	5	5	5.025	100.493		4.925	98.492	
	5	5	4.996	99.921		4.920	98.397	
120 %	5	6	6.027	100.447	100.399 ± 0.247	6.052	100.872	100.002 ± 1.652
	5	6	6.008	100.132		5.886	98.097	
	5	6	6.037	100.619		6.062	101.037	

Percentage recovery was in the range of 100.304 - 100.994% for Metformin and 98.988 - 100.002 % for Canagliflozin. LOD was 0.358 µg/ml and 0.335 µg/ml for Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively whereas LOQ was 1.085 µg/ml and 1.015 µg/ml for Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively. Method was robust with % RSD values <2% with the deliberate changes in the composition of mobile phase, changes in the pH or change in the flow rate. Applicability of the proposed method was evaluated by analyzing a synthetic mixture of marketed formulation (Invokamet, n=6) and the results are shown in Table 6. The assay results were 98.926 % and 98.526 % to labeled value of Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively in marketed tablet dosage form.

Table 6: Analysis of marketed formulation by developed method.

INVOKAMET Tablet	Synthetic mixture	
mg/tablet powder	Metformin (500 mg)	Canagliflozin (50 mg)
Assay (% of label claim*)	98.926±0.151	98.526±0.441
Mean ± S. D. (n=6)		
% RSD	0.57	0.69

Establishment of stability indicating method for assessment of degradation behavior

The stressed samples were assayed using developed RP-HPLC method. Following degradation behavior was observed under different stress conditions for the high-performance liquid chromatography studies on the combination of Metformin and Canagliflozin [Table 7-8].

Table 7: Percent degradation of Metformin with retention time of the degradation products.

Sr. No.	Conditions	Retention time of Metformin degradation products (min)	Average Peak area of Metformin Standard	% degradation of Metformin (n=5)	Average Peak area of Metformin in tablet (n=5)	% degradation of Metformin in tablet (n=5)
1	Untreated stock solution (10µg/ml)	3.47	779.798	-	-	-
2	Acid hydrolysis	4.01, 4.19	680.561	12.726	646.374	17.110
3	Alkali hydrolysis	4.15, 4.33	601.732	22.835	602.454	22.742
4	Oxidative degradation	3.97,4.43,4.94	669.313	14.168	654.393	16.082
5	Thermal degradation	3.91,4.06,4.58	568.767	27.062	557.754	28.475
6	Photolytic degradation	4.13,4.36,4.62	619.601	20.543	602.377	22.752

Table 8: Percent degradation of Canagliflozin with retention time of the degradation products.

Sr. No.	Conditions	Retention time of Cangliflozin degradation products (min)	Average Peak area of Cangliflozin Standard	% degradation of Cangliflozin (n=5)	Average Peak area of Cangliflozin in tablet (n=5)	% degradation of Cangliflozin in tablet (n=5)
1	Untreated stock solution (10µg/ml)	5.283	1007.218	-	-	-
2	Acid hydrolysis	5.98,6.29,6.72,7.29	817.280	18.858	793.604	21.208
3	Alkali hydrolysis	5.75,6.28	840.392	16.563	811.224	19.459
4	Oxidative degradation	6.86,7.42,8.38, 9.18	844.669	16.138	811.160	19.465
5	Thermal degradation	3.91,4.06,4.58, 6.92	764.701	24.078	746.485	25.886
6	Photolytic degradation	4.13,4.36,4.62,6.32	738.665	26.663	768.675	23.683

Significant degradation was observed in the presence of acidic, basic, neutral oxidative and photolytic stress conditions for Metformin and Canagliflozin respectively (n=5). Percentage Degradation for the standard drug was 13%, 23%, 14%, 27% and 20% for Metformin and 18%, 16%, 16%, 24% and 26% for Canagliflozin in the presence of acidic, basic, thermal, oxidative and photolytic degradation respectively. Percentage Degradation for the Metformin in INVOKAMET tablet was 17%, 22%, 16%, 28% and 22% in the presence of acidic, basic, thermal, oxidative and photolytic degradation respectively. Percentage degradation for Canagliflozin in INVOKAMET was 21%, 19%, 19%, 25% and 23% in the presence of acidic, basic, thermal, oxidative and photolytic degradation respectively. The percent degradation was calculated by the formula: % degradation = (Average peak area of untreated stock solution – average peak area of stock solution under specific degradation condition)/(average peak area of untreated stock solution) x 100

CONCLUSION

Proposed reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic method was able to successfully separate, identify and quantify Metformin and Canagliflozin simultaneously in the presence of their degradation products. This implies the stability indicating nature and specificity of the method. The developed validated stability indicating RP-HPLC method is simple, precise, accurate, robust and reproducible resolving all the degradation products from the analytes of interest. Thus, the proposed method can be applied for the determination of Metformin and Canagliflozin in bulk drug, pharmaceutical pre-formulation and formulations development studies in pharmaceutical research laboratories.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests.

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